

Surprisingly, in the plots with competition from *S. natans*, which is regarded as a major problem in rice fields in Java, yields were slightly higher and the number of productive tillers was 19% higher than in the weed-free check.

It is not known why, but the weight of *S. natans* competing with rice was lower than that of other weeds, and it is possible that the weed, which rapidly covers the surface of the water, reduced volatilization losses of applied nitrogen.

Effect of competition from various weed species on number of productive tillers and grain yield of transplanted rice IR34.

Competing weed species	Weed weight 70 DT ^a (t/ha)	Productive rice tillers (no./hill)	Rice yield (t/ha)
<i>Salvinia natans</i>	16.0	1.0	4.4
None	13.4	0	4.2
<i>Marsilea minuta</i>	13.7	2.5	3.4
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	11.2	1.4	3.1
<i>Cyperus</i> sp.	9.6	4.5	2.9
<i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	9.3	4.6	2.4
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	7.1	7.6	2.4
<i>M. vaginalis</i> + <i>Cyperus</i> sp.	7.5	9.8	2.3
<i>Cyperus</i> sp. + <i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	8.0	8.9	2.3
<i>M. vaginalis</i> + <i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	7.6	6.3	2.0
All + natural weed flora	8.8	6.5	1.9

^aDT = days after transplanting.

Treatments showed no significant differences in number of panicles per hill. The urea treatment showed the greatest number of grains per panicle, closely followed by *Azolla*-plus-fertilizer. The two *Azolla* treatments outdid the urea treatment in percentage of filled grains. *Azolla*-plus-fertilizer registered 132% as many filled grains per panicle as the control; the urea treatment registered 95%. Perhaps the *Azolla* treatment reduced sterility; further study of that question would be needed before drawing such a conclusion, however. The results clearly indicate that *Azolla* has a beneficial effect on yield of this rice variety.

Sulfur responses of lowland rice in South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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In many areas of South Sulawesi, Indonesia, farmers report little or no response of rice to urea in nitrogen-deficient areas. Because sulfur deficiency is the likely cause, studies of the response to ammonium sulfate were begun in 1976 (see table).

A decrease in the number of tillers was the major cause of yield reduction in sulfur-deficient plants. The plants showed yellowing of new growth. Symptoms generally were not uniform throughout a paddy; they were milder in areas with less waterlogging. To alleviate the problem farmers often drain paddies — a risky practice where there may not be sufficient water supply until harvest.

Response of lowland rice to additions of sulfur.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Control	Urea ^a	Ammonium sulfate
1	1.13	2.55	3.57
2	0.73	3.52	4.49
3	3.04	3.59	5.22
4	4.83	5.05	4.78
5	2.75	4.05	5.35
6	2.63	3.99	4.46
7	2.28	3.00	2.45
8	2.66	5.64	3.50

^aEqual rates of nitrogen.

Soil and crop management

Azolla utilization in rice culture

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Azolla can grow on nitrogen-free media with the aid of the nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*.

Under suitable conditions, it doubles its weight in 3 to 5 days by fixing 0.45 to 0.57 mg N/g fresh weight each day. Phosphorus, calcium, and iron are critical macronutrients in the water culture of *Azolla*. Temperatures above 31 °C inhibit its growth. *Azolla* that grew in field plots for 20 to 23 days accumulated about 24 kg N/ha. From October to January (106 days), five crops of *Azolla* were harvested, accumulating 120 kg N/ha.

Azolla nitrogen was released slowly; its availability to a single rice crop was about 70% of that of nitrogen from ammonium sulfate. A field was inoculated with *Azolla* at the time of transplanting of dry-season rice. Adding superphosphate improved *Azolla* growth; 40 days later the *Azolla* covered the surface and was incorporated into the

soil with a hand weeder. The result was a 13% increase in grain yield over a plot that was puddled in midseason without *Azolla*.

Effect of *Azolla* on yield of rice

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The effect of *Azolla* on rice yield was compared with the effect of urea fertilizer. Four treatments were used on rice variety BG 77-11 transplanted when 3 weeks old into 15-sq m plots:

- (1) control — no *Azolla*, no fertilizer;
- (2) *Azolla*, no fertilizer;
- (3) *Azolla* + a fertilizer mixture of phosphorus (67.3 kg/ha), potassium (43 kg/ha), and molybdenum (5.04 kg/ha); and
- (4) phosphorus, potassium, and molybdenum with urea (89.7 kg nitrogen/ha). When *Azolla* was used, it was inoculated 3 weeks before transplanting at 150 g/plot and again 1 week after transplanting. The urea was applied in three doses, 1, 5, and 9 weeks after transplanting.